

**THE EFFECTS OF FINTECH ON CREDIT PERFORMANCE TO SMES
GROWTH IN KENYA: A CASE STUDY IN NAIROBI COUNTY**

BY

EDWIN AMUGA O.

**A RESEARCH REPORT IN ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND INNOVATIONS
MANAGEMENT**

ABSTRACT

Small and medium enterprise financing is imperative to economic growth and improving living standards of a country's population. Access to financial products, including savings, insurance, credit, and payment of services, has increasingly led to an improved financial performance by Small and Medium Enterprises. SMEs have proven vital and significant in their contribution to economic growth as they play pivotal roles in job creation and poverty reduction. Despite this, these business formations have registered a high failure rate due to a lack of access to financial services. With the advent of technological development and application in modern society, Financial Technology has immensely influenced the financial and business sectors with such products as mobile saving and lending. These have resulted in efficiency, enhanced accountability, and have given SMEs a new lease of life due to the emergence of financial technology companies, FinTech, which have complemented the banking sector and provided local access to financial services with reduced formalities. In Kenya, FinTech companies include Tala, Branch, Stawika, Timiza, Okash, and Pesapata, which use the Peer to Peer lending (P2P) model to provide short-term lending to SMEs. This study sought to determine the effect of FinTech companies on credit performance to SME growth in Starehe sub-county, Nairobi, Kenya with an aim to make policy recommendations for improvement. The study adopted credit access theory and used a descriptive survey design to achieve its objectives.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

DECLARATION.....	Error! Bookmark not defined.
DEDICATION.....	Error! Bookmark not defined.
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT.....	Error! Bookmark not defined.
ABSTRACT.....	II
LIST OF TABLES.....	III
LIST OF FIGURES.....	Error! Bookmark not defined.
ACRONYMS.....	Error! Bookmark not defined.
CHAPTER ONE.....	Error! Bookmark not defined.
CHAPTER TWO.....	Error! Bookmark not defined.

CHAPTER ONE

Introduction

1.1 Study Background

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) play a critical role in economic growth in developing economies through wealth, job creation, and poverty alleviation. In the face of industrialization, SMEs have become the basis for fast economic growth. In that regard, Small and medium enterprises have become the socio-economic and political growth mediums in any country for growing economies. They are vital for the growth and expansion of businesses due to their large numbers and competition in the commercial sector leading to improved service delivery. Nevertheless, SMEs face operational challenges that lead to a high rate of failure.

Limited access to financial services and hence inadequate financing has been a significant hindrance to the growth of SMEs in Kenya. This is attributed to unfair regulatory and legal policies and prevailing banking operational lending policies that do not favor SMEs, such as the requirement to provide collaterals for loans. Restricted access to proper funding caused by the inadequate ability to provide SMEs with funding remains a considerable hindrance to the advancement of these business formations. Most Kenyan banks categorize SMEs as volatile and unsustainable in terms of risk. Due to these, a business-financing gap was created to provide SMEs with credit funding by many financial institutions and microfinance.

Business financing has been a daunting undertaking for the Kenyan Banking sector, and as a result, only a few SMEs barely manage to secure loans. The advent of financial technology companies has brought a new promise to fill in the business financing gap by providing financial services to SMEs. As a result, several financial institutions, governmental and non-governmental organizations, and even mainstream banks have moved in with tailored financial interventions to

enhance their profitability. Despite these efforts, the development of SMEs has not been fully realized due to shortcomings in credit performance.

1.1.1 Technology Application in Finance

The development of Information and Communication Technology has improved ways of doing business. The advent of technology has brought about an absolute prototype change in the functioning of financial institutions along with service delivery to customers in the banking sector. The adoption of technology in the financial industry, now referred to as financial technology, has conveyed customer service excellence, lessened transaction cost and time, and contributed to overall economic development. Financial Technology has been the catalyst behind improved efficiency and economic expansion at the business level.

Financial Technology (FinTech) is merging as the new form of financial service trade that merges Information and Communication Technology with fiscal services similar to payments, remittances, and asset management. FinTech refers to the technology-enabled financial solutions covering up the full service and product range conventionally offered by commercial banks.

FinTech is increasingly being employed in the financial sector and by businesses making it part of the fabric financial services ecosystem and banks. Small and medium enterprises, in particular, are benefiting from this to access financial services, regardless of their locations in the country, rural or urban. This is because financial technology is making financial services and products more available and accessible and reduces the transaction cost and time to transfer funds faster to businesses. This has been boosted by the affordability and accessibility of inexpensive mobile phones, smartphones, and cellular networks.

Financial institutions are using FinTech to offer financial products to small and medium businesses based on Peer-to-Peer crediting to loan businesses funds devoid of bureaucrat bank as a conciliator. The companies also use Blockchain digital ledger to display dealings more accessible, chronological, and openly.

1.1.2 Financial Products

Banks as financial institutions offer a range of financial services, including deposit-taking, investment capital, pension funds, and insurance funds. Essentially, financial products and services are designed to provide loans, savings, and risk management. Formal financial services include loans, account confirmation, account savings, debit and credit cards, insurance products, money transfer services, mobile banking, investment accounts, joint funds, retirement plans, private and government shares, stocks, and construction loans. Banks mainly provide these services as they are lawfully bound and accepted to offer formal financial services. On the other hand, informal financial services include those offered by individuals, persons, families, accomplices, friends, community groups, and social groups are characterized by no interest costs and are available in terms of loans and savings. These services are typified by abnormalities such as high losses due to dwindling negligence and fraud cases. The facilities providing these services are not standardized and thus difficult to categorize. Generally, these formations are not bound by law, and their effect on national growth is not easily quantifiable. This study focuses on financial technology products as indicators such as loans, savings, insurance as indicators of credit performance relevant to SMEs.

1.1.3 Financial performance

The growth of a business formation is determined by its operations, cost-effectiveness, and profitability. Profitability shows whether the firms can realize their objectives in terms of

revenue generation and soundness compared to the performance of their firms in different financial periods in a similar sector. Furthermore, such pointers as financial position statements enable business entities to gauge their financial performance and evaluate its viability and general performance.

Small and Medium Enterprises use such financial indicators as sales growth, return on investments, sales returns, dividend return per bond, and equity returns to gauge their financial performance. Furthermore, they use profits generated by assets (ROA), income on investment (ROI), gains related to equity (ROE), sales profit (ROS), revenue growth, share dividends, and dividend costs to measure their profitability growth of business and cost-effectiveness. This study captures financial performance measurement as market share, increase in sales, profits, and return on assets.

1.1.4 Financial technology products and financial performance

Financial technology products positively affect the financial performance of Small and Medium Enterprises. Lack of sufficient financial control information and reluctance of commercial players have long exposed small and medium enterprises to significant risks of mismanagement, lack of accountability, and poor financial performance. Financial technology financial services and products such as small savings, small loans, training, and micro-insurance have positively affected the financial performance of these small and medium-sized business entities. Financial technology companies quickly take over from micro finances to become the alleviators of poverty and unemployment and are independent of government and international players' support.

Access to Financial technology products and services, including savings, credit, micro-insurance, and payment services, have been boosting the financial capability of Small and

Medium Enterprises and have increased their survival chances. On the other hand, a lack of access to these products will negatively affect the financial performance of these small and medium businesses.

1.1.5 Small and Medium Enterprises in Kenya

Kenya's economy heavily relies on the performance of small and medium-sized businesses for its growth and advancement. In 2011, 79.8% of new job opportunity creation was attributed to the SME sector. A lot of emphasis has, as a result, been put on achieving vision 2030 economic pillar objectives on the roles played by small and medium enterprises in terms of job creation in the country. The MSE Act of 2012 provides for [proper legal and regulatory framework aimed at supporting the growth of SMEs through devolution as promised in the 2010 constitution. Nevertheless, the success of small and medium enterprises is pegged on the existence of appropriate institutional and regulatory policies in the face of the new 2010 Kenya constitution and devolution. Vision 2030 stipulates that small and medium businesses are critical instruments for the success of Kenya's economy. Small and medium enterprises are seen as an economic pillar for the realization of Vision 2030.

In a 1986 policy report, the Kenyan Government documented drives and objectives to enhance the growth of small and medium enterprises. This report highlighted several problems hampering the performance of small and medium enterprises and was later documented in the MSE policy report 1992 and subsequently reassessed in 2002. According to Kenya's goals of wealth distribution, industrialization, job creation, and poverty alleviation, these subsequent reviews gave birth to new regulatory structures inclined towards the growth of small and medium enterprises.

1.2 Research Problem

FinTech is merging as a new type of financial service business that incorporates technology with financial services such as payments, remittances, and asset management. It contended with conventional economic means in financial service delivery and aimed at extending access to SMEs and other customers outside the subdivision network and build opportunities for the productive cross.

Access to financial technology products leads to improved financial performance among small and medium enterprises. FinTech products have become fundamental in financing small and medium enterprise sectors in third-world economies worldwide. In light of these, the advent of FinTech has positively impacted the financial performance of SMEs. The importance of FinTech products on SME performance cannot be ignored and must therefore be factored in the economic growth policy of a country. SME failure worldwide has been a challenge to economic growth. SMEs in Africa have been noted to suffer from weak financial performance and a high rate of failure despite the Governments' efforts. In Kenya, up to 40% of small and medium enterprises go past their second anniversary, and up to 60% to not celebrate their fourth anniversary despite being significant contributors to job creation due to weak financing and poor credit performance.

Most related studies have studied microfinance, financial products, and performance of small and medium enterprises but left knowledge gaps on the effects of FinTech companies on the credit performance of SMEs. There have been studies conducted on the impact of microfinance on the financial performance of SMEs in many African countries, as well as access to credit by SMEs on their financial performance. These studies have presented contextual knowledge gaps and provide a chance to conduct a study locally to compare findings.

Locally, related studies have also been on the roles of microfinance institutions and how they affect job creation and poverty eradication. The studies have also studied SME financial constraints and noted a shortfall in access to financial services as an impediment to the growth of SMEs in the Country. Some studies have been on the association between microfinance institution loans and their impact on the financial performance of these small and medium businesses. The studies, equally, have presented conceptual knowledge gaps whose scope this study aims to widen to include FinTech products and their effects on SME credit performance to fill this gap. This study, therefore, sought to answer the question, what is the impact of FinTech companies on the credit performance of SMEs in Nairobi County, Starehe constituency?

1.3 Research Objectives

To determine the effect of FinTech companies on the credit performance of SMEs in Nairobi County, Starehe constituency

1.4 Value of the study

Policymakers in the financial sector will find the study findings valuable due to the new knowledge presented. The Central Bank of Kenya will also find the conclusions of this study beneficial in its roles of regulating the financial institution in Kenya and develop a proper policy framework allowing easy access to credit.

Financial institutions and mainstream banks will also find the findings valuable in informing the best policy formulation and market penetration on the best products to offer clients to increase their market share. This study sought to establish the effect of such FinTech products as credit, insurance, savings, internet, and mobile banking products on SME credit and thus

financial performance. Consequently, this study will and financial institutions to understand SME reception to each product.

The study findings will also benefit SMEs operating in Nairobi and the rest of the country and Africa at large as they face similar challenges on financing. Hence, the results will provide valuable insights into the need to embrace the promises of financial technology in growth of the economy and create jobs. By linking financial products to technology, SMEs can understand the most significant financial products for their development.

Scholars and researchers will also benefit from the findings of this study as it lays down the foundation for future research. This study presented knowledge gaps and recommendations for further studies on the research subject. This will help expand the topic of FinTech products offered by financial institutions.

CHAPTER TWO

Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

The chapter reviews past literature on financial technology and the credit performance of small and medium enterprises. The section also gives the theoretical basis and outlines the empirical studies on how technology has impacted the credit performance of small and medium enterprises. This chapter also illustrates a conceptual model that portrays the correlation between independent variables and dependent variables. The chapter concludes with a summary of the literature review.

2.2 Theoretical Review

This study adopted several theories to determine the effects of financial technology companies on the credit performance of SMEs. The theories include the credit access theory, microfinance theory, financial growth life cycle theory, and adverse selection theory

This part discusses the presumptions holding the correlation between financial technology and credit performance. The presumptions adopted are the acceptance model and innovation theory diffusion.

2.2.1 Technology Acceptance Model

Davis (1989) developed the Technology Acceptance Model posits a relationship between the innovation acceptance by the user and the evident use of use and the technology usefulness. This theory argues that several issues determine the decision about how and how technology is to be used. Such issues encompass the apparent convenience and perceived user-friendliness of the technology in consideration for employment.

In a study, Legris, Ingram, and Colletette (2003) argue that they proved the reliability Technology acceptance Model in clarifying and envisaging customer actions of Information Technology. Sabi (2014) posits that the theory is the most reliable and applied in most of the reviewed articles.

The theory is relevant and applied in this study since it is a factor by which the adoption of Financial Technology by Small and medium enterprises can be rationalized. One of the critical factors to adopting the theory is how the users react to a newly introduced technology. This study researched to determine the percentage of Small and medium enterprises that have adopted FinTech in their operations. This is aimed at determining the association between the usefulness of FinTech and the perception of users.

2.2.1 Credit Access theory

The theory was developed by Stiglitz and Weiss (1981) and outlines how lack of information results in faulty financial markets in third countries. Financial institutions offering loans to small and medium enterprises focus on the interests of the loans and the risks involved. As a result, most financial institutions providing loans to small and medium enterprises scrutinize and effectively monitor their borrowers compared to other investors. The credit access theory suggests that information asymmetry on such issues as interest rates and price changes affects credit access.

The credit access theory is relevant to the study since it explains the micro-credit financial products. This theory also correlates changes in price and information asymmetry to credit access. According to the theory, credit necessitation for a collateral requirement for loans is due to information asymmetry. Because high-risk borrowers have more wealth and collateral for loans, low-risk borrowers experience more difficulty securing collateral and loan access.

Consequently, small and medium enterprises that cannot meet the collateral requirements miss on credit, thus negatively affecting their performance.

2.2.3 Microfinance Credit theory

Microfinance institutions emerged in the mid 1950s through the Loan Board Schemes. They were formed to facilitate credit to local individuals with small trading business loans. Loans provision to groups is heralded as a significant information source for microfinance institutions. This is hailed as a remedy when loan markets face downfalls, specifically to cover up for the asymmetries brought about by information. Typically, imperfect information systems have resulted in moral hazards and adverse selection. Failure to get the right information results in adverse selection as the lender does not get the correct information about the borrower's volatility.

Rahman (2010) argues that the chances of borrow default increase with risk levels. The increased default risk calls for the higher interest rate costs to risk borrowers to compensate for the failure. As a result, less risky ones should be subjected to lower interest costs. On the other hand, based on information asymmetry, financial institutions impose higher interest rate costs.

The theory is relevant in this study since it helps explain the rationale behind the interest rates levied on credit. As per the theory, lenders charge high-interest rates on borrowers they perceive to have higher risks. Moreover, information asymmetry affects the amount of interest charged on borrowers. It is believed that high interest rates are charged due to the increased risk of lending in case of information asymmetry.

2.2.4 Financial Growth Life Cycle Theory

Berger and Udellin proposed the theory in 1998 and argued that the chances of small and medium enterprises to secure funding widens as they grow in size. The Financial growth life

cycle theory factors in the existence of varying nature of collateral and information explain funds availability to firms over time.

Berger and Udellin (1998) posit that firms plan for a funding series during their operation period on financial pecking orders due to information asymmetry. The theory argues that a firm increases its chances of acquiring credit as time goes by until they gain better and bigger loan and market equity funding. Small and medium enterprises grow in stages as per their equity.

The theory is essential to the study in explaining how financial technology products influence the credit performance of small and medium enterprises. The approach establishes a correlation between financial technology products and SME financial growth. The theory also offers an understanding of accessing technology financial products for SME size growth and widening opportunities for securing funding.

2.2.4 Adverse Selection theory

Stiglitz and Weiss developed the theory of adverse selection in 1981. The theory posits that financial institutions levy interest cost is significant to determining the risks for each borrower resulting in adverse selection. Borrowers' subsequent actions constitute the incentives' effect. The transaction type is determined by the interest rate cost. Information asymmetry brings about these effects in the credit market. Consequently, banks chose to utilize interest cost rates to evaluate borrowers' risk.

The researchers also argue that enormous interest rate costs entice FinTech companies to initiate tasks to firms with little success opportunities resulting in a moral hazard problem. This problem forces financial institutions to formulate loan contract terms to attract low-risk borrowers drastically. The equilibrium rate of interest is achieved when the credit demand supersedes the supply.

This theory also correlates financial technology products with the credit performance of small and medium enterprises. It further argues that the collateral and loan sums determine how borrowers approach financial institutions and the profitability of approaching banks for loans.

2.3 Credit performance determinants

The credit performance determinants refer to the tools and facilities financial institutions deliver. This section discusses financial technology products, including saving, credit, insurance, and internet banking products.

2.3.1 Micro Saving products

Most FinTech companies in developing economies, including Mshwari, KCB-MPESA, and M-Akiba offer saving services vital to families, individuals, and small businesses. The companies offer small businesses and households a cheap alternative to acquire foodstuffs and small stocks when income sources are inadequate. FinTech companies also complement investments in the form of personal and tangible loans. Saving and pooling activities and facilities are poorly developed in developing economies, aggravated by a lack of will to draft strategies to ameliorate it. Poverty remains one of the leading causes of poor savings and loaning cheap, timely, and secure culture. In low-income countries, most savings are done through merry-go-round forms of savings and in the form of such properties as livestock and physical goods. Traditional saving models include the perennial theory and long-term income models. Persons reduce their expenses and evaluate the amount to save for future expenditure concerning the prevailing costs.

On the other hand, saving mechanisms and committing to it are well developed in high-income economies. Some of the services in this regard include medical funds, savings funds, education funds, pension funds, and investment funds. These services are unavailable or poorly

developed for the underprivileged in low-income economies. Several theories are in existence in developing economies regarding the generation of these facilities. This led to the provision of these ventures in small scale with small costs by FinTech companies.

2.3.2 Micro Credit Products

Credit risk refers to the inability to repay loans as per the contractual agreement due to unsafe lending practices. On the other hand, credit performance refers to the ability of these small and medium enterprises to repay their loans per the contractual agreements. The loan values as an asset are computed by establishing the total loans minus allowances for loan losses. Loan loss allowances are a provision or reserve determined showing the loan amounts made past due dates and likely to continue remaining in default.

The loan repayment weaknesses led to the financial crunch of 2007-2009. This loan repayment weakness and the inability to make loan losses led to capital depletion and losses in Kenyan banks in the 1980s, 1990s, and 2008. Consequently, to reduce the risk of capital depletion, the capital market regulators resorted to tightening the examination criteria and loan reserve policies and accept other voluntary measures to lessen risks.

2.3.3 Micro Insurance products

The main reason for microinsurance is to act as the omission of economic resources or services in case of economic recessions, accidents, fatalities or sicknesses occur that would financially affect operations of small and medium enterprises and their owners and families. In Kenya, M-Bima is an example of FinTech Microinsurance product. They are typified with a risk control system to allow the less small and medium businesses to recompensate for proper state-funded plan shortage.

Small insurance policies provide the less privileged with insulation against certain risks instead of standard premium charges estimated to the concerned chance and risk fees. Small and medium enterprises may use it to procure standardized insurance. The premium versus claims, reinsurance, and administrative cost experience amount indicates the production and contribution this.

2.3.4 Internet Banking Solutions

Internet Banking is an extension of banking services obtained and served in digital conduits, including costs, capital, funds, covers, allowances, and fiscal data. Digital channels include the internet, point of sale devices, electronically enabled cards, and computerized devices.

Digital Financial services offer a convenient and secure transactional environment to the public. M-shwari, as an M-banking extension in the Kenyan financial market, involves using mobile devices to access services and transact simple banking businesses. M-banking is a reaction to vibrant and erratic business settings that need FinTech companies to create new information-sharing policies.

2.4 Empirical Review

In a study aimed at determining the effect of the short and long-run associations between the economic growth of small and medium enterprises and microinsurance development in Nigeria between 1986 and 2010, Olalekan and Taiwo (2013) revealed that microinsurance had had a positive and significant association with the SME economic growth in Nigeria. The study's findings also showed that the presence of long-run association between the microinsurance developments integrated with the Nigerian SME economic growth. This study centered on Nigerian insurance products.

Ahiawodzi (2012) studied the determinants to accessing credit by small and medium enterprises in Ghana. The study sampled 78 SMEs and utilized questionnaires in its data collection. Correlations and regression analyses were utilized in the analysis of data. The study found that SME access to financial services led to better credit performance. Nkeobuna (2012), in a survey of the correlation between microcredit and SME performance in Ghana, used correlation and regression analysis of primary data collected and found that microcredit products positively impacted the financial performance of small and medium enterprises in both service and agricultural sector. The study centered on access to credit, calling for deeper conceptual insight focusing on financial products to fill the literature and knowledge space presented in the study.

Sakthi and Kumar (2011) found a correlation between FinTech financial products and entrepreneurial development. The study results showed that most African populations borrowed cash to buy food, and only a few did so to start and support businesses. The study conclusions include the argument that most Africans do not have the know-how to become successful entrepreneurs. The study established that there is a general lack of individual determination, fear of ownership sharing, failed partnership, and proper technical and management skills.

Werner (2009), in a comparative study to determine the variation of microinsurance products between India and Bangladesh, found that accessing micro-insurance products led to increased use of essential health services. It also established that the products grew ventures into riskier business ventures by Small and medium enterprises. This study, carried out in an emerging economy, calls for research to cover the contextual knowledge gap and investigate the same topic in such contexts as Kenya to compare the findings with a joint position of the argument.

Wachira (2011) studied microcredit usage by small and medium enterprises In Kenya and used primary data and inferential analysis. The study found that loan lending terms including interest rates and collateral required impacted SME credit access. Macharia (2012), in a study that used primary data, established a correlation between SMEs' micro credit products and credit performance in Kenya. The study utilized regression analysis and indicated that these products are significant to SME growth and credit performance. The study also brought forward a conceptual knowledge gap with the main focus on credit financing products. The study focused on three more financial products, including microinsurance, micro-savings, and internet banking products, to establish a correlation between them and financial performance.

Nyabuga (2013), in a study, established that informal financial formations improved access to credit by Small and medium enterprises operated by Kibera women resulting in empowerment. The correlation findings revealed a positive and significant correlation between credit access, management, and enterprise growth by SMEs owned and run by women. Nyabuga (2013) also concluded that the informal financial sector positively impacted the development of SMEs in Kibera and widened the investigation scope. This study calls for further studies to fill in the contextual knowledge gap by centering on other areas of Nairobi County to enhance heterogeneity and achieve more generalizable findings.

Muthoka (2012) sought to establish a link between FinTech products and financial stability among SMEs in Nairobi East District, used primary data, and ran a regression model to establish a correlation. This study found that FinTech credit and financial products resulted in SME financial growth and stability. The study also widened the investigation scope and called for more research to fill in the knowledge gap by focusing on other parts of Nairobi for heterogeneity.

Mokua (2013) conducted a study that focused on the effect of management skills and collateral measures on SME growth in Kenya and adopted a descriptive research design in Kisii County SMEs. The findings of the research revealed that lack of finance access affected the growth of SMEs. It also found that bureaucratic procedures caused insufficient finances to the enterprises from financial institutions. The study also exposed a conceptual knowledge gap that this study seeks to fill.

2.5 Conceptual Framework

The independent variables for the study are FinTech products, namely, savings (savings interest rates, FinTech savings accounts, minimum savings allowed), credit (loan processing periods, securities needed, loan interest), insurance (premiums, cover types, affordability), and internet banking (Internet banking, mobile phone deposits, mobile phone bill payment). Bruno et al. (2017) posit that these products such as small savings, small loans, savings, training, and small insurance reflect the credit performance of small and medium enterprises. The study assumes that good financial performance means good credit performance. Therefore, the present study expected to establish a positive correlation among these variables, the Fintech products.

2.6 Literature Review Summary

The literature review shows that studies Olalekan and Taiwo (2013) on the effect of the short and long-run association between the SME economic growth and microinsurance development in Nigeria, Ahiawodzi (2012) on SME credit access determinants in Ghana, and Nkeobuna (2012) associating micro-credit services with SME performances in Ghana showed contextual and literature gaps that needed to be extensively studied. The studies were done outside Kenya, and the findings can neither be generalized nor adopted for the case of Kenya and Starehe constituency particularly. The studies carried out locally by Wachira (2011) to identify

the determinants of Kenyan SME micro-credit usage, Muthoka (2012) to establish a correlation between FinTech products and financial stability of SMEs and Mokuu (2012) to determine the effect of management skills and collateral measures for Kenyan SME growth present knowledge gaps to be filled by the present study.

2.7 Research Gaps

The fore-going literature is evidence that the Financial products affect the financial performance of SMEs but have not been fully identified and addressed adequately. It is also evident that it has not been established why the Financial products have positive impacts on Kenya's SME performance. The literature review shows presence of literature on the financial performance of SMEs as affected by different financial products but fail to point out the effects of Fintech products on credit performance. This study aims to fill in the research gap by looking into the effects of financial technology products on the credit performance of SMEs.

CHAPTER THREE

Research Methodology

3.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the study methodologies used in the research design, the population and sample size. The chapter also indicates the data collection and the analysis methods used in the study.

3.2 Research design

This study used a descriptive survey design. Blumberg, Cooper, and Schneider (2014) define descriptive survey design as the design used to present situations and collect data over several units. The study is suitable for the study since it plays a role in answering 'what' and 'which' and describes the phenomena of small and medium enterprises' financial performance. The study application of the research design also helps in answering the study questions. The research design was thus apt in establishing the effect of FinTech companies on the credit performance of small and medium enterprises.

3.3 Population

The study targets a population consisting of 250 small and medium enterprises operating within Starehe constituency, Nairobi County, per the company register 2016. The study targeted the owners of small and medium enterprises. The distribution of the small and medium enterprises across the wards in Starehe constituency is indicated in Table 2.1 below.

Table 3.1 Target population

Starehe Wards	Target Population
Nairobi Central	632
Ngara	603
Pangani	661
Landimawe	662
Nairobi South(South B)	580
Total	3138

Source: Company Registrar 2018

3.5 Sample

The study employed stratified random sampling to include and reduce bias. In determining the sample size, the study used Yamane's (1967) formula $n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$

Where n= Sample size

N= Total number of SME's in Starehe constituency

e=marginal error (5%)

Substituting the values gave a sample size of 400 SMEs operating in Starehe Constituency,

Nairobi County

$$n=(30252/(1+30252(0.05)^2)$$

$$n=400$$

Stratified sampling was used to distribute these SMEs into strata due to the heterogeneity of the population.

The sample distribution was as the following Table

Table 3.2 Sample Size

Starehe Wards	Target Population	Sample Size	Percentage
Nairobi Central	632	81	21
Ngara	603	76	19
Pangani	661	89	22
Landimawe	662	79	20
Nairobi South(South B)	580	75	18
Total	3138	400	

3.5 Data Collection

The study used questionnaires to gather quantitative primary data. The analysis unit was SMEs, and owners of more than one SMEs counted as one. Closed-ended questions were used in the questionnaires and yielded quantitative data. The questionnaires were divided into six sections where the first section dwelt on demographic information about the respondents while the remaining five sections asked on the variables of the study in a five point Likert form.

Questionnaires and critical informant interview were used. Using more than one instrument helps in supplementing information, thus making reliable findings and conclusions. The questionnaire was set to include demographic data of the respondents, the aspects of SME embracement of FinTech products, and the anticipated effects of the engaged approaches.

3.5.1 Piloting of Research Instruments

The instruments were tested based on a small sample of the population. For the questionnaire, five potential respondents were selected to answer the questions. From the five, two will also be interviewed to ascertain the applicability of the tool. Piloting of the instrument was recommended for increasing the device's validity and ensuring there were no ambiguous questions. The researchers identified issues that needed reframing as well as eliminating unnecessary parts of the questionnaire. The time required to conduct one interview and the time required to fill one questionnaire were established during the tools' piloting process.

3.6 Data Analysis

The study utilized descriptive and inferential analysis methods in analyzing the data since the data collected was quantitative. The descriptive analysis involved using means, standard deviation, percentages, correlation, and trends to study the variables over a range of time. Correlational analysis was utilized to establish the relationship between the study variables. A multivariate regression model was employed to show the effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable.

3.6.1 Analytical Model

The study used a regression model to study the correlation between the study variables. The FinTech products, the variables, were measured by savings products, credit products, insurance

products, and internet banking products. The dependent variable, credit performance, was measured in terms of growth in sales and profits. Multivariate regression analysis was employed due to the presence of more than one predictor. The model below was used.

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \epsilon$$

Where Y- Credit performance of the SMEs

X₁- Savings products

X₂- Credit products

X₃- Insurance products

X₄- Internet Banking

ε-Error term

β-Predictor Variables Coefficients

3.6.2 Variable Measurement

The four study independent variables were savings products, credit products, micro-insurance, and internet banking products, and credit performance of the SMEs as the dependent variables.

Table 3.3 Variable Measurement

Variable	Type	Measurement	Questions in the Questionnaire
Savings products	Independent Variable	The interest rate on savings Minimum saving	B1-B4

		amount allowed	
Credit service	Independent Variable	Interest on loans Loan processing period	C1-C4
Insurance product	Independent Variable	Amount of insurance Insurance cover offered	D1-D4
Internet Banking	Control Variable	M-deposit services M-bill payment	E1-E4
Credit performance	Dependent Variable	Gross credit	F1-F4

3.6.3: Test of Significance

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) was carried out using the F test to test the significance of the model. T statistic was conducted to test model coefficient significance. The study also conducted a 5% level of significance relationship and established it at a 95% confidence level to establish if the effects of the FinTech products have significance.

3.7 Testing for Validity and Reliability/Dependability and Credibility

3.7.1 Validity Issues

After identifying the right respondents, a pilot study was conducted to test the questions' ambiguity, stimulus, consistency, and material. Researchers were careful when interviewing stakeholders at a convenient time so that it is done when the respondents are ready, as this served to maximize internal validity. The researchers were also careful when making the questionnaire easy to avoid human error and interpretive forgers. The selection of adequate respondent

numbers and other measures based on pretest outside the school to prevent sensitization and behavior change by participants will ensure validity.

3.7.2 Reliability Issues

A purposeful collection assures the reliability of competent participants through snowballing. Researchers were careful to avoid bias in compiling data and clearing raw ones, fashioning and entering them into the statistical packages for social scientists (SPSS) for accessible and analyzable data format, SPSS version 16 was used. The research assistants were adequately trained to ensure consistency in all the procedures. The result reproducibility in all other settings was assured using standard research protocols, quality control, and universal rules. The periods that the participants stayed with the questionnaire were also reduced to minimize the random error. Self-administered questions ensured that the bias of the interviewer was avoided. The fatigue among the respondents was decreased by using short single-sentence instructions, and the questionnaires were sub-divided into sections. The key informants' interviews were made quick and direct, whereas depth sessions were immediate and lasting five to ten minutes to minimize respondent fatigue.

3.7.3 Data Analysis Procedures

The research objectives guided the data analysis process. The collected information underwent verification before being subjected to the theoretical framework and analyzed through analytical and logical arguments using qualitative approaches. The qualitative information was analyzed through thematic and content analysis before being integrated/triangulated with the primary data findings. Respondents' quotes, views, and ideas were quoted to support the findings and enhance the validity of the results.

For the primary data, information collected through the questionnaires was subjected to cleaning processes (Etikan, Alkassim & Abubakar, 2016). Data were coded to make it easy for entry into the Statistical Package for Social Scientists (SPSS) software for processing. Once the data had been entered into the SPSS, result output was run, leading to the desired output. From the output, the researchers analyzed and interpreted the data while writing the remaining chapters of the study.

Descriptive statistics were applied to summarize collected data employing tabulated description (tables), graphical representation (graphs and charts), and commentary (in-depth narration of the results). As indicated above, the presentation of data, graphical representations, and tables was prioritized to enable the straightforward presentation of the results.

3.8 Conclusions

The chain-referral sampling procedures will be used because they can be used to identify respondents who will lead the researcher to others that are unknown but are potential respondents. Therefore, the researcher will be able to locate more respondents, approach them for their participation in the study, and ask them for further referral of more respondents until the required sample size is achieved. The study will also adopt a descriptive cross-sectional survey due to its significance in facilitating more comprehensive data sources coverage. The use of both methods, quantitative and qualitative, strengthens the research model as it increases result validity and reliability.

References

- Etikan, I., Alkassim, R., & Abubakar, S. (2016). Comparison of Snowball Sampling and Sequential Sampling Technique. *Biometrics & Biostatistics International Journal*, 3(1), 00055.
- Ahiawodzi, A. K., & Adade, T. C. (2012). Access to credit and growth of small and medium scale enterprises in the Ho municipality of Ghana. *British Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Sciences*, 6(2), 34-51.
- Berger, A. N., & Udell, G. F. (1998). The economics of small business finance: The roles of private equity and debt markets in the financial growth cycle. *Journal of banking & finance*, 22(6-8), 613-673.
- Macharia, P. (2012). The effects of access to finance on micro and small enterprises investment growth in Ongata Rongai Township. *Unpublished MBA Project, University of Nairobi*.
- Makena, K. (2011). Challenges faced by small & medium enterprises in accessing finance in Kiambu town. *School of Business, University of Nairobi*.
- Mbithe, M. N. (2013). *The Effects of Microfinance Services on the Growth of Small and Medium Enterprises in Machakos County* (Doctoral dissertation).
- Mokua, L. O., & Ngugi, P. K. (2013). Determinants of effective corporate entrepreneurship in the banking industry in Kenya: A case of Equity Bank Limited. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Entrepreneurship*, 1(5), 936-952.
- Muthoka, J. M. (2012). *Effect of microfinance on financial sustainability of small and medium enterprises in Nairobi East District* (Doctoral dissertation).

